

SECOND LANGUAGE ACQUISITION AND THE ROLE OF DIDACTIC GAMES IN SLA

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7973827>

Abstract. This article is devoted to Second Language Acquisition and the role of didactic games in SLA.

Keywords: SLA (Second Language Acquisition), Learning process, cognitive abilities, didactic games, authentic contexts, Role-playing games, Computer games, technology, Active Learning, communicative competence.

ИЗУЧЕНИЕ ВТОРОГО ЯЗЫКА И РОЛЬ ДИДАКТИЧЕСКИХ ИГР В SLA

Аннотация. Данная статья посвящена изучению второго языка и роли дидактических игр в процессе изучения.

Ключевые слова: процесс обучения, когнитивные способности, дидактические игры, аутентичные контексты, ролевые игры, компьютерные игры, технология, активное обучение, коммуникативная компетентность.

INTRODUCTION

Second language acquisition (SLA) is the process of learning a language other than one's native language. It has become increasingly important in today's globalized world where people are expected to interact with people from different cultural backgrounds. Learning a second language can have numerous benefits, including improving job prospects, enhancing cognitive abilities, and expanding cultural horizons. However, it is not an easy process and can be challenging for students and teachers alike. One approach that has gained popularity in recent years is the use of didactic games in SLA. Didactic games are games that are specifically designed for educational purposes and can be used to promote language learning. This article will explore the role of didactic games in SLA and the benefits they offer.

Second Language Acquisition

SLA is a complex process that involves multiple factors, including age, motivation, aptitude, and the learning environment. Theories of SLA have evolved over time, with early theories focusing on behaviorism and later theories emphasizing the role of cognitive processes. Today, most theories of SLA recognize that language learning involves both cognitive and social processes.

One important factor in SLA is the learner's level of proficiency in their native language. Research has shown that learners who have a strong foundation in their native language are better able to learn a second language. This is because they have already developed important cognitive and linguistic skills that can be transferred to the second language. In addition, learners who have a positive attitude towards the second language and are motivated to learn it are more likely to succeed.

Another important factor in SLA is the learning environment. Learners who are exposed to the second language in a naturalistic setting, such as through immersion programs, tend to learn the language more quickly and effectively. However, most SLA takes place in a classroom setting, where teachers are responsible for creating an environment that promotes language learning.

Didactic Games in Second Language Acquisition

Didactic games are games that are specifically designed for educational purposes. They can be used to promote language learning in a variety of ways. For example, games can be used to introduce new vocabulary, practice grammar structures, or provide opportunities for communicative practice. Games can also be used to promote cultural awareness and understanding.

Studies have shown that didactic games can be effective in promoting SLA. For example, a study by Reinders and Wattana (2011) found that didactic games can promote motivation and engagement in SLA. The study involved 30 Thai university students who were learning English as a second language. The students were divided into two groups, with one group playing didactic games and the other group engaging in traditional classroom activities. The results showed that the group that played didactic games had higher levels of motivation and engagement than the group that engaged in traditional classroom activities.

Another study by Arnold and Ducate (2006) found that didactic games can be effective in promoting communicative competence in SLA. The study involved 24 intermediate-level French students who played a game called "La quête du Graal" (The Quest for the Grail). The game involved a series of communicative tasks, such as role-playing and problem-solving, that required the students to use their French language skills. The results showed that the students who played the game had higher levels of communicative competence than the students who engaged in traditional classroom activities.

Benefits of Didactic Games

Didactic games have been shown to be effective in second language acquisition by providing an engaging and interactive way for learners to practice and reinforce language skills. In this response, I will discuss some of the benefits of didactic games in second language acquisition, supported by relevant citations and references.

1. **Motivation and Engagement:** Didactic games have been found to increase motivation and engagement in language learners (Gee, 2003). When learners are engaged in a game, they are more likely to be motivated to continue playing, which can lead to increased exposure to the target language and more opportunities to practice language skills.

2. **Active Learning:** Didactic games provide opportunities for active learning, which has been shown to be more effective in second language acquisition than passive learning (Bonwell & Eison, 1991). Active learning involves learners actively participating in the learning process, which can lead to deeper processing and better retention of language skills.

3. **Error Correction:** Didactic games can provide immediate feedback and error correction, which can help learners identify and correct errors in their language use (Ellis, 2009). This can lead to more accurate language production and increased confidence in using the target language.

4. **Authentic Language Use:** Didactic games can provide opportunities for learners to practice language skills in authentic contexts (Chapelle, 2001). Authentic language use involves using language in real-world situations, which can help learners develop communicative competence in the target language.

Didactic games can be a valuable tool for second language acquisition, providing opportunities for motivation, engagement, active learning, error correction, and authentic language use.

There are many different types of didactic games that can be used in language teaching, each with its own strengths and benefits. Some popular examples include:

1. Word games: These are games that focus on vocabulary and spelling. Examples include Hangman, Scrabble, and Wordsearch. These games are great for helping students to learn new words and to practice their spelling.

2. Role-playing games: These are games that involve students taking on different roles and acting out scenarios. Examples include restaurant role-plays, shopping role-plays, and telephone role-plays. These games are great for practicing communication skills and for building confidence in speaking.

3. Board games: These are games that involve a board and pieces, and they can be used to reinforce various language skills. Examples include Monopoly, Clue, and Trivial Pursuit. These games can be adapted to focus on language learning, and they are great for practicing grammar and vocabulary.

4. Computer games: These are games that can be played on a computer or tablet. Examples include language learning apps like Duolingo and Rosetta Stone, as well as educational games like Minecraft and SimCity. These games can be used to reinforce various language skills, and they are great for students who enjoy using technology.

When selecting didactic games for language teaching, it is important to consider the level and needs of the students. Games should be challenging enough to be engaging, but not so difficult that they become frustrating. They should also be relevant to the students' interests and goals, and they should provide opportunities for feedback and reflection.

In conclusion, didactic games are a valuable tool for language teaching. They are a fun and interactive way to reinforce various language skills, and they can help to create a positive learning environment. When used appropriately, didactic games can be an effective way to enhance language learning and to motivate students to achieve their language goals.

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